

PSYCHOLOGICAL MECHANISMS OF FORMING SPIRITUAL AND MORAL EDUCATION AMONG STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the pedagogical mechanisms of forming spiritual and moral education among students from a scientific and theoretical perspective. The role of the educational process, pedagogical technologies, interactive methods, and the social environment in students' moral development is revealed. Scientific conclusions and practical recommendations are presented.

Introduction: In the context of globalization, the spiritual and moral education of the younger generation is one of the important factors in the development of society. In particular, young students are recognized as the main social stratum that determines the intellectual and spiritual potential of society. Therefore, the formation of their spiritual and moral education is one of the urgent tasks facing the education system [1]. During the period when young students are formed as individuals, moral views, social responsibility and civic position are strengthened. In this process, the correct selection of pedagogical mechanisms determines the effectiveness of education. First, let's dwell separately on what spiritual and moral education is.

Spiritual and moral education- is a continuous and purposeful pedagogical process aimed at forming in a person correct behavior, high spirituality, national and universal values, social responsibility and moral consciousness. This education is not only about imparting knowledge, but also forms the inner world, beliefs and life position of a person.

Spiritual and moral education serves to develop such qualities as:

- the ability to distinguish between good and evil,
- adherence to the rules of society,
- a sense of responsibility for one's actions,
- respect for others.

Spiritual and moral education is a continuous pedagogical process aimed at ensuring the unity of moral consciousness, moral feelings and moral behavior in a person, carried out on the basis of national and universal values. The scientific and pedagogical essence of spiritual and moral education. Scientific and theoretical foundations of spiritual and moral education

Spiritual and moral education is a complex and multifaceted pedagogical process aimed at forming a person in accordance with the requirements of society. This process includes the

development of a person's moral consciousness, social responsibility, culture of behavior and attitude to spiritual values. In pedagogical theory, spiritual and moral education is recognized as a key component of personal development. In the life of young students, the stage of higher education is an important period when personal worldview, beliefs and social position are formed. It is during this period that students develop the skills of independent thinking, making moral choices and feeling social responsibility. Therefore, there is a need to organize spiritual and moral education in higher education institutions on a scientifically based basis.

Features of the spiritual and moral development of students

Students have their own psychological and social characteristics, and an active social environment plays an important role in their spiritual and moral formation. During this period, a person undergoes a process of self-awareness, setting life goals, and choosing a professional direction. Factors influencing the spiritual development of students include family upbringing, the pedagogical environment in an educational institution, peer influence, and the media. In particular, a healthy spiritual environment formed in a higher educational institution has a positive effect on the moral views and behavior of a student. Pedagogical mechanisms for the formation of spiritual and moral education.

Educational orientation of educational content

Enriching the content of education in terms of spirituality and morality is one of the important pedagogical mechanisms of educating students. Each subject, through its content, should form ethical thinking, professional responsibility, and social activism in students. The educational process based on interdisciplinary integration broadens students' spiritual outlook and creates an opportunity for a comprehensive approach to ethical problems

The possibilities of interactive psychological methods

Interactive methods provide active participation of students, teach them to think independently and make moral decisions. Discussion, debate, case studies, role-playing games and problem situations develop moral responsibility in students. Through such methods, students acquire the skills of freely expressing their opinions, respecting the opinions of others and reaching compromises.

Organization of psychological work based on a person-oriented approach.

A person-oriented approach involves organizing the educational process taking into account the individual interests, needs and abilities of the student. This approach strengthens the internal motivation of students and accelerates their spiritual development. The teacher must create conditions for independent thinking of the student in the educational process, support his social activity.

The role of the teacher in spiritual and moral education

The teacher is not only a source of knowledge for the student, but also a moral example. A teacher's personal culture, speech etiquette, behavior, and professional responsibility directly affect the spiritual formation of students. Through his or her activities, a teacher can develop qualities such as justice, honesty, responsibility, and humanity in students

Educational environment and social cooperation

The educational environment created in a higher educational institution is an important factor in the spiritual and moral development of the student. Cooperation between the family, educational institution and society ensures the continuity of education. Spiritual and

educational events, social projects and volunteer activities strengthen the civic position of students. If each pedagogical staff is active in these processes, good and effective results can be achieved.

Innovative approaches to spiritual and moral education

The use of modern information and communication technologies increases the effectiveness of spiritual and moral education. Electronic platforms, online discussions and digital resources serve to develop students' spiritual literacy. Innovative approaches ensure that students respond consciously to modern social problems.

Assessment of the effectiveness of spiritual and moral education

Evaluation of the effectiveness of the educational process is an important stage of pedagogical activity. The assessment criteria take into account students' moral behavior, social activity, and attitude to spiritual values. Educational work is improved based on the results of monitoring and analysis.

In conclusion, the formation of spiritual and moral education in students is a complex, multifaceted, and continuous psychological process that is manifested on the basis of a person's internal needs, value system, motivation, and interaction with the social environment. In this process, psychological mechanisms such as identification, interiorization, reflection, emotional-affectiveness and social learning play an important role. Through these mechanisms, students develop a moral consciousness, a sense of responsibility, social activity and loyalty to national and universal values. Also, a healthy psychological environment in an educational institution, the role of the pedagogical personality as an example, and the systematic organization of educational activities are the main factors that increase the effectiveness of spiritual and moral education. Therefore, one of the urgent tasks is to implement an approach based on psychological mechanisms in the upbringing of a harmonious personality in students.

References:

1. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Yangi O'zbekiston strategiyasi. – Toshkent: O'zbekiston, 2021.
2. Davletshin M.G. Umumiy psixologiya. – Toshkent: O'qituvchi, 2012.
3. G'oziev E.G. Psixologiya. – Toshkent: O'qituvchi, 2014.
4. Vygotskiy L.S. Psixologiya rivojlanish nazariyasi. Moskva: Pedagogika
5. Leontev A.N. Faoliyat, ong va shaxs. – Moskva: Politizdat, 1977.
6. Bandura A. Social Learning Theory. - Englewood Cliffs: Prentice Hall.
7. Kohlberg L. Essays on Moral Development. Vol. 1: The Philosophy of Moral Development. – San Francisco: Harper & Row, 1981.
8. Abdurahmonov F.R. Ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiya psixologiyasi. – Toshkent: Fan, 2018